

KIDNEY TUMOR ON A PATIENT WITH A LONG TERM REGULAR HEMODIALYSIS

Cokorda Agung Wahyu Purnamasidhi^{*1}, Ni Made Renny A Rena^{*}, Ketut Suega^{*} and Raka Widiana[□]

^{*}Division of Hematology and Medical Oncology, Internal Medicine; Department Udayana University-Sanglah General Hospital Denpasar, Indonesia., [□]Division of Nephrology and hypertension, Internal Medicine; Department Udayana University-Sanglah General Hospital Denpasar, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT A 31-year-old Balinese male, who have undergone hemodialysis for nine years and then diagnosed with renal cell carcinoma (RCC). The basis of the diagnosis was from the increased abdominal complaints and left hip pain. The investigation with ultrasound and abdominal CT scan obtained the mass on the left kidney, and after the radical nephrectomy surgery, the examination of the pathology found multicystic kidney disease with extensive necrosis with malignant markings in some preparations. Kidney tumours rarely occur in patients undergoing long-term hemodialysis. This is allegedly due to the inactivation of a tumour suppressor gene. Therefore, periodic checks are necessary to detect the presence of malignancy in patients undergoing long-term hemodialysis. As these cases are rarely reported in Indonesia and there is often a delay in diagnosis, it is expected to add insight to early diagnosis and provide optimal therapy to prolong patient life expectancy. Early detection and treatment are expected to provide a better prognosis and prolong the patient's life expectancy.

KEYWORDS Kidney tumour, Long term hemodialysis, Renal Cell Carcinoma

Introduction

Since the first hemodialysis machine was demonstrated in the 1940s, this machine is thought to be capable of prolonging a person's life and curing uremia symptoms. In the 1970s, the spread of this machine has expanded and can save the lives of patients who have acute kidney failure or end-stage renal failure. [1]

Today, almost millions of people around the world are benefiting from long-term regular hemodialysis. The number of patients undergoing hemodialysis increases by 5% annually. Improving the quality of replacement therapy for kidney function has an impact on increasing the life expectancy of patients. Apart

from that, several studies have concluded that an increase in cases of malignancy in people undergoing hemodialysis. [2]

A cohort study of patients with terminal renal failure in Australia reported a high incidence of cancer in dialysis patients compared with those not undergoing dialysis with an incidence rate of 1.35 (95% IK = 1.27 to 1.45). [3] Even recent studies report, of 454 patients undergoing hemodialysis, 12 percent of them died from malignancy. It is the third after cardiovascular disease (52%) and infectious diseases (25%). [4]

The mechanism of carcinogenesis in long term dialysis remains unclear. Chronic oxidative stress, decreased immune system, viral infection and some renal diseases such as renal cyst disease are thought to be risk factors causing the emergence of malignancy. Also, it should be noted that patients with terminal stage kidney disease have genomic disorders that may also have a role in cancer formation. This genomic disorder may be caused by the buildup of uremic toxins such as advanced glycation end products (ages) or homocysteine. [5] In this case, we reported patients diagnosed with a kidney tumour and have undergone long regular hemodialysis. As these cases are rarely reported in Indonesia, and there is often a delay in diagnosis, it is expected to add insight to early diagnosis and provide optimal therapy to prolong patient life expectancy.

Copyright © 2019 by the International Sci Ink Press Ltd
DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.kidney-tumour-hemodialysis
First Received: March 15, 2019
Accepted: April 16, 2019
Associate Editor: Ivan Inkov (BG)

¹Division of Hematology and Medical Oncology, Internal Medicine; Department Udayana University-Sanglah General Hospital Denpasar, Indonesia.; Email: purnamasidhi@unud.ac.id

Case report

A 31-year-old Balinese male came to Sanglah Hospital in July 2014. The patient came with a stomach enlargement complaint.

The stomach is felt enlarged for two months before hospitalized. The stomach is felt increasingly more significant, especially on the left abdomen. In addition to enlarging, the patient also felt the pain in the left abdomen. The pain is getting worse for two days before hospitality.

The patient has been diagnosed with chronic renal failure since nine years ago and has been undergoing routine hemodialysis for two times a week. Patients had used Continuous Ambulatory Peritoneal Dialysis (CAPD) about one year ago but failed. Patients also have hypertension and have been taking medication for a long time. The patient's sister also suffered terminal kidney failure and died almost a year ago.

The patient is fully alert with the blood pressure of 130/80 mmHg. Regular pulse was increased 108 times/minute, with the patient's respiratory rate is still within normal limits. The patient's pain scale is obtained [4]. The eye conjunctival examination is pale. The patient's heart and lung examinations are all within normal limits. On abdominal examination, the abdomen is distended, with a maximum abdominal circumference of 98 cm. From palpation, there was a palpable mass in the left lumbar region with solid consistency, approximately 10x12 cm in size, with tenderness. Pain positive in the left positive costovertebral angle.

Laboratory results obtained urea nitrogen serum 44.08 mg / dL, serum creatinine 6.51 mg / dL, serum calcium 10.28 mg / dL, serum inorganic phosphor 6.02 mg / dL, serum albumin 3.7 g / dL, hemoglobin 6.36 g / dL, MCV 81 fL, MCH 28 pg, white blood cell count $7, 2 \times 10^3 / \mu\text{L}$ and platelet count $173 \times 10^3 / \mu\text{L}$.

From ultrasound examination, a large mass with an unresolved border on the left kidney covering almost all of the renal parenchyma with the impression corresponds to a heterogeneous solid mass present in the left kidney (Fig. 1). While the results of abdominal CT scan of patients found in the left kidney there is a solid heterogeneous mass with cystic components in it that fill the left kidney, it firmly bordered with uneven edges, measuring 10.9 x 10.6 x 22.7 cm which with contrast partially contrast enhancement (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Multiple cysts in the left kidney from the patient's ultrasound on July 2012 (A); USG in July 2014 demonstrates the presence of heterogeneous solid mass (B).

At that time the patient was diagnosed with a suspicious left kidney tumour towards the renal cell carcinoma (RCC) and polycystic kidney right. On August 19, 2014, the patient underwent radical nephrectomy surgery and performed an anatomical examination of anatomical pathology. From the results of the ex-

Figure 2: The heterogeneous solid mass that fills the left kidney, firmly bound with uneven edges, measuring 10.9 x 10.6 x 22.7 cm.

amination was found multicystic kidney disease with extensive necrosis with malignant markings in some preparations (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Pathology of Patient's Kidney.

Discussion

Patients with terminal stage renal failure due to diabetes, nephroangiosclerosis, polycystic kidney disease, urinary tract abnormalities and glomerular disorders have significantly benefited from renal replacement therapy and are even able to prolong the life expectancy of a person. However, chronic renal failure with prolonged dialysis makes them in a chronic oxidative stress condition that is closely related to the occurrence of cancer. This chronic oxidative stress situation results from the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) capable of damaging cellular structures, including lipid membranes, proteins and nucleic acids. [6]

Some risk factors that can trigger the growth of cancer cells in the kidney organs include smoking, excess weight or obesity, some work related to pesticides, asbestos and cadmium metal. In

addition to that, some things are unavoidable risk factors, such as races where Afro-American race is more commonly affected, male sex is twice as risky, and family history suffers from renal malignancy. [7]

Patients suffering from terminal stage kidney failure by undergoing regular hemodialysis have a high risk of developing kidney tumours. In these patients, the patient has nearly nine years undergoing regular hemodialysis. This situation made patients more at risk for kidney tumours. Dunnill et al. (1977) reported the first 14 of 30 patients undergoing hemodialysis at the time of autopsy to find a tumour in their kidneys. [8] In 2005, the United States Renal Data System (USRDS), found an increased incidence of renal tumours in patients undergoing prolonged hemodialysis. [9] Ishikawa et al. (2002) state that, the length of a person performing hemodialysis effect on the occurrence of kidney tumours in the person. The 10-year study says that the emergence of one of the largest kidney tumours in the second year and the ninth year of a person undergoing hemodialysis. [10]

This patient is experiencing terminal renal failure, which was caused due to known polycystic kidney disease from ultrasound examination. The patient's sister also died because of terminal renal failure. This linkage of renal disease between these families makes us suspect the presence of genetic diseases in these patients. Autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease (ADPKD) is the most common disease of hereditary renal disorder, which occurs in 8-10% of terminal renal failure patients. [11] Keith et al. (1994) reported that RCC as a severe complication of ADPKD, but the incidence of RCC in ADPKD is still controversial because the number of patients with ADPKD diagnosis remains unclear. To detect RCC in ADPKD is not an easy matter, although using a CT scan or MRI, this is because the renal architectural structure has been damaged by ADPKD. [12]

A long duration of hemodialysis is thought to contribute to the development of renal tumours in patients with terminal renal failure. Sumiko et al. (2005) reported that connexin (Cx) 32, a gap junction that acts as a suppressor gene tumour, fails to function due to hypermethylation of the Cx 32 gene promoter region that occurs in patients undergoing hemodialysis. [13]

Connexin (Cx) 32 is a protein encoded by the Gap junction beta-1 protein gene (GJB1). The Cx 32 function is still not widely known, but several studies have shown that this gene acts as a suppressor gene tumour in renal tumour growth. [14] Hirai et al. (2003) also observed the same thing. They suggest that hypermethylation in the promoter region Cx 32 causes regulation to decrease from Cx 32 to facilitate the onset of RCC. [15]

In these patients, radical nephrectomy surgery was performed. In this type of operation, the entire kidney including the adrenal glands and surrounding tissues are removed. Surgery is the main therapy of RCC, though other treatments can be considered such as radiotherapy or chemotherapy in RCC although the results are not as good as surgery. In some developed countries, they also consider immunological therapy, but the results are still unsatisfactory, and the side effects are still too risky. [6,16] The result of the examination of patient's pathology showed off multicystic kidney disease with extensive necrosis with a mark of malignancy in some dosage. Some studies say the duration of hemodialysis affected the type of pathology of renal tumours. Sassa et al. (2012) reported that in Japan, patients with hemodialysis duration less than ten years showed clear cell carcinoma as the most RCC type. Whereas in patients undergoing hemodialysis between 10-20 years obtained papillary cell carcinoma and

acquired cystic disease of the kidney associated RCC as the most common form. Whereas in patients more than 20 years undergoing hemodialysis obtained renal sarcoma type as the most tumours. [17] This is also conveyed by Matsuda et al. (2011), that the duration of hemodialysis determines the type of cell pathology of RCC. Where patients are undergoing hemodialysis for more than ten years if RCC is found, the prognosis will be worse. [18] Therefore, it is advisable if the patient has undergone long-term hemodialysis periodic examination needs to be done to detect the emergence of malignancy.

Summary

A 31-year-old Balinese male, who have undergone hemodialysis for nine years and then diagnosed with renal cell carcinoma (RCC). The basis of the diagnosis was from the increased abdominal complaints and left hip pain. The patient underwent radical nephrectomy surgery, and investigation of the pathology found multicystic kidney disease with extensive necrosis with malignant markings in some preparations. Kidney tumours have rarely occurred in patients undergoing long-term hemodialysis. Therefore, periodic checks are necessary to detect the presence of malignancy in patients undergoing long-term hemodialysis.

Competing Interests

There were no financial supports or relationships between authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interest.

Funding

None.

References

1. Mandayam S, Shahinian VB. Are Chronic dialysis patients at increased risk of cancer?. *J Nephrol.* 2008; 21:166-174.
2. Janus N, Launay-Vacher V, Thyss A, Bolanger H, Moranne O, Islam M, Durande J, Ducret M, Juillard L, Soltani Z, Motte G, Rottembourg J, Deray G, Thariat J. Management of anticancer treatment in patients under chronic dialysis: result of the multicentric study. *Annals of Oncology.* 2013; 24:501-507.
3. Vajdic C, McDonald S, McCredie M. Cancer incidence before and after kidney transplantation. *JAMA.* 2006; 296:2823-31.
4. Uchida K, Shoda J, Sugahara S. Comparison and survival of patients receiving hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis in a single center. *Adv Perit Dial.* 2007; 23: 144-149.
5. Higgins P, Rouse R. Renal Cell Carcinoma Associated with End Stage Renal Disease. *Mod Pathol.* 2009; 22 Suppl 2:2-23.
6. American Cancer Society. Kidney Cancer in adult - Renal cell carcinoma overview. 2014. Accessed from www.cancer.org 16 August 2014.
7. Ishikawa I. 2008. Acquired cystic disease of the kidney and renal cell carcinoma 7th Ed. New York. McGraw Hill Medical. p1386-1400.

8. Siegel S, Sandler M, Alpern M, Pealberg J. CT of renal cell carcinoma in patients on chronic hemodialysis. *AJR*. 1998; 150:583-585.
9. Bretan P, Busch M, Hricak H, Williams R. Chronic Renal Failure: a significant risk factor in the development of acquired renal cyst and renal cell carcinoma. *Cancer J*. 2006; 57:1871-79.
10. Ishikawa I, Saito Y, Shikura N, Kitada H, Shinoda A, Suzuki S. Ten-Year Prospective Study on the Development of Renal Cell Carcinoma in Dialysis Patients. *J Kid Int. Supp*. 2002; 41:167-69.
11. Nishimura H, Ubara Y, Nakamura M, Nakanishi S, Sawa N, Hoshino J, Suwabe T, Takemoto F. Renal cell carcinoma in autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease. *Jam Soc Nephrol*. 2009; 54: 165-68.
12. Keith VE, Torress VE, King B. Renal cell carcinoma in autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease. *JAm Soc Nephrol*. 1994; 4:1661-69.
13. Sumiko S, Hiromi H, Hiromi S, Keiko F, Shigeto K, Taiichiro S, Toyohiko A. Prevention of renal cell carcinoma from hemodialysis patients by regulating epigenetic factors. *J Kid Int*. 2005; 67:2506-09.
14. Yano T, Ino F, Kobayashi K, Yonezawa Y, Suzuki K, Asano R. Hypermethylation of the CpG island of connexin 32, a candidate tumor suppressor gene in renal cell carcinomas from hemodialysis patients. *J Patol*. 2003; 26; 234-37.
15. Hirai A, Yano T, Nishikawa K, Suzuki K, Asano R, Satoh H, Hagiwara K, Yamasaki H. Down-regulation of connexin 32 gene expression through DNA methylation in a human renal cell carcinoma cell. *Am J Nephrol*. 2003; 23(3):172-77.
16. Fujimoto E, Sato H, Sirai S, Nagashima Y, Virgona N, Hagiwara K, Yamasaki H, Ueno K, Yano T. Inhibition of Src activity enhances the tumor-suppressive effect of the connexin 32 gene in Caki-1 renal cancer cells. *Oncology reports*. 2006. 15: 1359-65.
17. Sassa N, Hattori R, Tsuzuki T, Watarai Y, Fukatsu A, Katsuno S, Nishikimi T, Fujita T, Ohmae K, Gotoh M. Renal cell carcinomas in haemodialysis patients: does haemodialysis duration influence pathological cell types and prognosis?. *Nephrol Dial Transplant*. 2012; 26: 1677-82.
18. Matsuda H, Kihara K, Fujii Y, Koga F, Saito K, Sakura M, Okada Y, Kawakami S. Renal Cell carcinoma in dialysis patients with end-stage renal disease: focus on surgery and pathology. *JTok med univ*. 2011.p31-44.